

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Students’ Challenges in Learning Evolution and their Level of Mastery: An Input to An Enhancement Program

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Received: 09 March, 2022

Accepted: 11 April, 2022

Published: 13 April, 2022

Abstract

Determining the students’ mastery level and identifying the challenges encountered by them in learning evolution to provide a basis for developing a program enhancing the students’ mastery level is this research’s purpose. The quantitative and qualitative research approaches were employed in the conduct of this study. A questionnaire was administered to the respondents who were randomly selected to collect information needed for this study. An interview was also done to further understand and clarify students’ responses. It was found that students have an average mastery level in learning evolution which needs further enhancement to achieve the educational aims of a high mastery level. Also, it was proven that students’ mastery levels differ if they are grouped according to gender. This means that gender has something to do with their levels of mastering evolution concepts. Despite various educational efforts, students still faced challenges in learning evolution which includes issues with their learning styles, abilities, and interest, the lack of educational resources and materials, and insufficient knowledge of evolution concepts and theories. These challenges implicate their learning, hence, designing a program that best suits the students’ needs is required to enhance their mastery level.

Keywords: Evolution; Learning Challenges; Mastery level

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1. Introduction

Biology is one of the subjects in the Senior High School where students are taught about life, the concept of diversity, how organisms interact and how energy is transformed, and evolution. With their exposure to the subject, the students are able to better understand the underlying concepts of Biology (Department of Education [DepEd], 2016).

One of the most important concepts that were discussed in Biology is Evolution. "Relevance, mechanisms, evidence/bases, and theories of evolution" is the content standard for the evolution topic in General Biology as a special subject, while "unifying themes in the study of life" is the content standard for a core subject (Teacher PH, 2021). To be specific, the competencies in teaching evolution cover "explaining how the structural and developmental characteristics and relatedness of DNA sequences are used in classifying living things, identifying the unique/distinctive characteristics of a specific taxon relative to other taxa, and describing species diversity and cladistics, including the types of evidence

and procedures that can be used to establish evolutionary relationships" (DepEd, 2016).

Evolution is defined as a slow process of change by which organisms have acquired their distinguishing characteristics. It has been going on since the earth was formed billions of years ago. The more common theories on evolutions are Lamark’s theory of Acquired Inheritance and Darwin’s Theory of Natural Selection (Murray, 2018). Evolution is described as the change in heritable traits of biological populations over successive generations (Ashraf & Sarfraz, 2016).

Evolutionary theory is continuously developing. New theoretical considerations based on new techniques and empirical data have contributed to a more refined knowledge of how evolution works in the biological world and beyond over the years and decades (Hanish & Eirdosh, 2020). However, It is perceived that learning evolution is contentious since many individuals feel that the notion of evolution contradicts their religious beliefs.